

STUDIES IN THE COAGULATION OF COLLOIDS. PART XVIII.
THE " ZONAL EFFECT " AND ANTINORMAL CHANGE
OF OPACITY DURING THE SLOW COAGULATION
OF COLLOID MANGANESE DIOXIDE.

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In Part XIII of this series (Joshi and S. J. Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 311) the observation was recorded, it would appear for the first time in the field of coagulation kinetics, that during the *slow* electrolytic coagulation of colloid $Mn(O)_2$, the intensity of light transmitted (measured by means of a sensitive thermopile and Broca galvanometer) diminished 'zonally', that is, through discontinuities with respect to the coagulation time. Further evidence in this line was obtained by colorimetric measurements of the coagulation of the same sol using mercurous sulphate as the coagulant (Joshi and Purushottam, *Current Science*, 1936, 4, 870). In view of the obvious bearing of these results on the current theories of the mechanism of coagulation and of its kinetics, it was considered desirable to study this effect in more detail.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Colloid manganese dioxide was prepared and its colloid content determined as described in an earlier paper (Joshi and Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 217). The last quantity was 1.5 g. of MnO_2 per litre in the *coagulating mixture*. The concentrations of the coagulants employed, *viz.*, solutions of different strengths of acetic acid (Fig. 1, 2), potassium chloride (Fig. 3, 4) and barium chloride (Fig. 5) are expressed in millimols per litre (mm.), also in the *mixture*. The opacity was determined by means of a Duboscq colorimeter as described previously (Joshi and Kulkarni, *ibid.*, 1936, 13, 441). The variations of opacity during these coagulations are shown graphically in Figs. 1-5; these are selected as typical out of a greater number of curves actually studied, where different origins are employed to prevent overlapping of curves and for economy of space, the appropriate scale units are indicated in the corresponding parts of the diagrams.

FIG. 1.

DISCUSSION.

From the very beginning of observation of the coagulation phenomena an increase of opacity (turbidity) has been taken by colloid chemists to be in general an index of coagulation. Indeed, this assumption is tacitly implied in numerous quantitative investigations of the kinetics of coagulation. Our results disclose now a remarkable restriction in the generality of the correctness of the above assumption. It is seen that there is the familiar overall increase of opacity during the early stages of coagulation, except when the two lowest concentrations of KCl were employed (*cf.* curves 1, 2, Fig. 3); in these latter coagulations, contrary to the usual experience, the opacity has diminished. It is also interesting to observe that a diminution of opacity is

produced subsequent to the initial phase of coagulation which latter is characterised by the familiar rise of opacity. It must be pointed out here that as is customary in these kinetic measurements, the opacity observations were discontinued as soon as the coagulating mixture showed the least sensible production of any optical heterogeneities due to the coagulum. An

FIG. 2.

increase of the particle-size due to micellar coalescence is the chief, if not the only, process constituting coagulation. To this, chiefly, is to be ascribed the familiar rise of opacity of a colloid; other factors also contribute to the effect, *viz.*, increase of opacity, such as the nature of the micellar surface, their average effective shape, number per unit volume, the characteristic optical absorption of the dispersed material and that constituting the continuous medium; their refractivities, optical densities and states of hydration; and lastly, perhaps the electrical charge. These cannot be determined

directly to any thing like a satisfactory accuracy. Consequently, except perhaps in the case of a few monodisperse sols, the theory of the optics of a colloid even in the pure state is still largely in an uncertain state, despite notable contributions in the line (for references, *cf.* Joshi and Sarkar, *loc. cit.*). Reference may, however, be made to two deductions of fairly general applicability due to (i) Rayleigh (*Phil. Mag.*, 1871, 4, 107, 274, 447) and (ii) Tolman (*cf.* Ware, "Chemistry of the Colloidal State" 2nd Ed., 1936, New York, p. 99). They have obtained respectively, the following expressions for I , the opacity of a colloid of strength c in g. per unit volume :

$$I = k.c.d^3 \dots \dots \text{for small particles} \dots \dots (i)$$

$$I = k_1.c/d \dots \dots \text{for large particles} \dots \dots (ii)$$

k and k_1 are proportional constants and d , the micellar diameter. It follows from these equations that for a given constant mass of the colloid in two solutions, I , the opacity will increase with an increase of d for small particles in other systems. With large d , I will diminish by increase in d . The results of Bechhold and Hebbler (*Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 31, 70) on the opacities of differently sized suspensions of barium sulphate show that I increases progressively with increase of d over a certain range, *viz.*, 2.5 to 800 $\mu\mu$; thereafter, I diminishes for further increase in d .

FIG. 3.

Our results showing an initial rise and a subsequent fall in opacity during coagulation can, therefore, be, *in part*, ascribed to a progressive increase of the micellar size during coagulation. That some additional factors are involved is shown by the fact when the smallest concentrations of KCl were used (curves 1, 2, Fig. 3) there is instead of a rise of opacity, a *diminution*. On the above considerations, this might suggest perhaps a decrease of the particle-size. This last is by no means unlikely. Considerable evidence is available in the literature that addition of very small amounts of coagulants to a colloid usually imparts an increase in stability, apparently suggestive of a diminution of size. It is, however, not unlikely that this result might also be derived from adsorption of ions carrying a like charge or of the neutral molecules, or what is more likely, of both. It might also come about by diminished hydration. It was emphasised in an earlier paper (Joshi and Kulkarni, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 439) that *the opacity of a colloid might be, in part, more than a merely micellar property; it might also arise by a macroscopic, bulk effect of the system as a*

FIG. 4.

whole, that is, by the continuous medium and the dispersed material acting together in a common net-work or a body effect. It was observed that such a postulate was necessary from a consideration of the viscous behaviour of colloids (*loc. cit.*). This gives an additional meaning to the factor of micellar hydration, which is seen to be variable during coagulation. Observation of characteristic facts is needed for suggesting the lines for a theoretical elucidation of the working of the above factors. As such, our result that besides the familiar phase, during which opacity increases by coagulation, there is another, characterised by a decrease of this quantity, is interesting.

Another remarkable feature of the foregoing opacity-time curves is that not only the familiar increase of opacity during coagulation, but also its reverse during the latter stage is not time-continuous but zonal. By considering the series of curves for different concentrations of a given coagulant

(cf. especially Figs 1, 2 and 3, 4), it is seen that this *zonal effect* (as indicated by the number of discontinuities in a given section of the coagulation-time curve) is reduced by using very high and very low concentrations of the electrolyte. It is maximum for moderate values. This is fully in agreement with numerous results on the refractometric observations from these laboratories on the *zonal effect* during various coagulations (Joshi and S. J. Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 141; Joshi and Panikkar, *ibid.*, 1936, **13**, 309; Joshi and N. H. Rao, *ibid.*, 1936, **13**, 775; Joshi and T. M. Menon, *ibid.*, 1937, **14**, 103; Joshi and Sarkar, *J. Bombay Univ.*, 1935, **4**, 140; Joshi and S. J. Rao, *Kolloid Z.*, 1936, **76**, 145; *Feltchem. Umsch.*, 1936, **3**, 36). The earlier results on viscosity changes during numerous *slow* coagulations, from these laboratories have also suggested in the main the same conclusion, that is, discontinuities on viscosity—time curves are least conspicuous during very rapid and very slow coagulations (Joshi and Viswanath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 329; Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, 1933, **10**, 599; Joshi and Nanjappa, *ibid.*, 1934, **11**, 135; Joshi and Iyengar, *ibid.*, 1934, **11**, 555, 573; Joshi and Panikkar, *ibid.*, 1934, **11**, 797; also, *J. chim. Phys.*, 1935, **32**, 455; *Proc. Acad. Sci. U.P.*, 1935, **5**, 41).

S U M M A R Y

Results are given for the variation of I , the opacity (determined colorimetrically) of colloid MnO_2 when coagulated by differently concentrated solutions of CH_3COOH , KCl and $BaCl_2$. The opacity—time curves show two sections. In the first section I increases with time; in the second, the opposite. The last was also observed when but small quantities of the coagulators were employed. Furthermore, during both the stages when I showed the familiar increase or otherwise, the change was time-discontinuous or '*zonal*.' In agreement with earlier findings from these laboratories, '*zonal effect*' was most pronounced for *medium* concentrations of the coagulant.

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